

Greener Journal of Environmental Management and Public Safety

ISSN: 2354-2276

Submitted: 11/12/2015

Accepted: 15/12/2015

Published: 29/02/2016

DOI: <http://doi.org/10.15580/GJEMPS.2016.1.100915143>

An Assessment of Energy Poverty in Zimbabwe's Urban Communities: The Case of Marondera

By

Rejoice Madobi

Research Article (DOI <http://doi.org/10.15580/GJEMPS.2016.1.100915143>)

An Assessment of Energy Poverty in Zimbabwe's Urban Communities: The Case of Marondera

Rejoice Madobi

Zimbabwe Open University, P. O. Box 758 Marondera
E-mail: joymadobi@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT

Though access to adequate, clean, reliable, sustainable and modern energy sources is a priority for poverty alleviation, provision and access to such energy sources has continued to be a challenge in Zimbabwe in the face of poor economic performance and increasing urban poverty levels. This study sought to assess energy poverty in Marondera Urban. Three residential areas and 120 respondents were selected for the study using a combination of purposive and random sampling techniques. A descriptive survey design was employed. Interviews, questionnaires and documentary analysis were used to collect data. The study found out that the residents of Marondera are energy poor as they have limited energy options; in the absence of electricity residents are forced to rely on traditional energy sources. This study recommends that energy and other related policies be pro poor and that more research into energy sources be done to increase the energy choices for urban dwellers.

Key words: energy, energy poverty, modern energy, traditional energy.

1. INTRODUCTION

Access to modern energy sources is necessary for economic growth and improving living conditions at household level (World Bank, 2010). To meet basic human needs and alleviate poverty there is need to make efficient and reliable cleaner sources of energy available and accessible. A special excerpt of the World Energy Outlook of 2010 noted that the United Nations' MDG goal of eradicating extreme poverty by 2015 was not reachable without improving energy access (IEA/UNDP/UNIDO, 2010). This therefore implies that there is a link between the source of energy used by a household and poverty.

Globally, two million deaths occur annually from pneumonia, chronic lung disease, and lung cancer which are associated with exposure to indoor air pollution resulting from the burning of biomass energy (crop residue, cow dung and fuel wood) in traditional ways (UNDP/WHO, 2009). Cleaner and sustainable household energy therefore, has the potential to improve the health of people in developing countries where according to UNDP/WHO (2009), 99% of the diseases (associated with indoor air pollution) occur. It is estimated that premature deaths from indoor air pollution would be greater than those from HIV/AIDS, Malaria and Tuberculosis by year 2030 (IEA/UNDP/UNIDO, 2010). Availability and access to sufficient and reliable cleaner energy sources is also necessary for the operation of health institutions and schools. Access to clean energy also ensures adequate access to clean safe water and agricultural productivity as well as job creation.

Collection of fuel wood also takes a lot of time in rural areas and keeps people (particularly women and children) away from other productive pursuits. According to Wodon and Blackden (2006), societal norms tend to assign reproductive roles such as taking care of the children, the sick and the elderly as well as preparing food, cleaning, collecting fuel wood and water and other household chores to women. Therefore, reducing the consumption of traditional biomass energy can help save time and create better livelihood opportunities. The use of electricity in the evening extends work and study hours and contributes to productivity and educational achievements.

More to that, the burning of solid fuels in open areas and traditional stoves also has significant global warming effects, due to incomplete combustion of carbon. There is need therefore to address energy challenges not only in terms of industries and the productive sector but also for domestic uses if climate change is to be mitigated and environmental sustainability maintained. Forests are being lost in developing countries due to unsustainable harvesting for energy and other purposes. In Zimbabwe, wood fuel provides (61%) of the total energy supply and it is estimated that 330,000ha of forest area, or over 60 million trees are lost each year. Demand for wood fuel in Zimbabwe already exceeds supply in heavily populated provinces of Manicaland, Mashonaland East, the Midlands and Masvingo (Zimbabwe National Energy Policy, undated).

Although energy was not explicitly mentioned in the MDGs, the World Summit on Sustainable Development held in Johannesburg in 2002 recognised that the provision of modern energy services was critical for the attainment of these goals (Zimbabwe National Energy Policy, Undated). In other words, without addressing energy issues it is not possible to alleviate or eradicate poverty. To emphasise the importance of

energy, A new post 2015 synthesis (post MDG) report (Road to Dignity by 2030: Ending Poverty, Transforming All Lives and Protecting the Planet) launched by the UN Secretary General on the 4th of December has 17 sustainable goals and one of its goals is to ensure access to affordable, reliable, sustainable and modern energy for all.

Despite the importance of modern energy, half the world's population live without modern energy; 1.5 billion people in developing countries lack access to electricity. It is estimated that more than 80% of people without electricity access live either in sub-Saharan Africa or in South Asia. While sub-Saharan Africa makes up about 14% of the total population of developing countries, it accounts for almost 40% of the population without electricity access (UNDP/WHO, 2009). An estimated 620 million people in sub-Saharan Africa do not have access to electricity, and for those that do have it, supply is often insufficient, unreliable and costly (OECD/IEA, 2014).

Due to the importance and the figures pointing to energy poverty across the globe, the United Nations (UN) launched the Sustainable Energy for All initiative in 2011 and declared the 2014-2024 the Decade of Sustainable Energy for All (SE4A). The declaration focuses on universal energy access, renewable energy and energy efficiency. One of the objectives of the Zimbabwe National Energy Policy is to increase energy access to all sectors of the economy.

Despite various efforts and strategies to ensure the availability of and access to adequate clean energy supply, access to energy remains a challenge not only in Zimbabwe but globally. Though rural areas have been known to lag behind in terms of access to modern energy (World Bank, 2010); the use of traditional biomass fuels has also become common in the urban areas. The poor in both rural and urban areas are the most disadvantaged. While the urban poor do have some form of access to alternative source of energy particularly electricity, it is usually unreliable thus forcing the urban dwellers to resort to unclean and unsustainable energy sources.

1.1. Definition of Key Terms

Energy (for the purposes of this study, energy is taken to include fuels such as petroleum products (kerosene, petrol, diesel) and biomass (firewood, charcoal, agricultural wastes, dung), power (electricity) which can be from a number of sources (fossil fuel based or renewable).

Energy poverty is the absence of sufficient choice in accessing adequate, affordable, reliable, clean, high quality, safe and benign energy services to support economic and human development

Alternative energy sources are energy sources that are alternative to traditional fuels or traditional energy sources (fuel wood and coal). Alternative energy sources are generally environmentally friendly.

Modern fuels is used to refer to electricity, liquid fuels (such as kerosene), and gaseous fuels (such as Liquefied Petroleum Gas (LPG), natural gas), and excludes traditional biomass and coal.

1.2. Research Problem

Clean and sustainable energy sources are important to human and economic development; yet a greater percentage of people in developing countries still lack access to it. Though energy poor people live in both rural and urban areas, many studies on availability of and accessibility to alternative energy sources and the consequences on human well being have been focused on rural areas where poverty levels are higher and dependence on traditional fuels is noticeably great. A number of factors such as rapid and rampant urbanisation, poor economic performance as well as increase in urban poverty to mention just a few have, created challenges for the energy sector in Zimbabwe. One of the objectives of Zimbabwe's National Energy Policy is therefore to increase access by all the sectors of the economy to affordable energy and to diversify the supply options. This paper therefore sought to assess the energy poverty in selected residential areas of Marondera urban.

1.3. Research Objectives

The main objective of this study was to assess energy poverty in selected residential areas of Marondera Urban. The specific objectives were to;

1. Identify the main sources of energy for the residents of Marondera Urban.
2. Determine factors that have influenced the access to alternative energy sources in Marondera.
3. Examine the challenges faced in Marondera due to lack of access to alternative sources of energy.
4. Explore strategies employed by the residents of Marondera to cope with the energy challenges.

1.4. Research questions

The research study was guided by the following research questions;

1. What are the main sources of energy for the residents of Marondera?
2. Which factors have influenced the ability by Marondera urban residents to access alternative energy sources?
3. To what extent are alternative sources of energy accessible to the residents of Marondera Urban?
4. Which strategies are employed by the residents of Marondera to cope with the energy challenges?

1.5. Scope of the study

The study focused on urban household energy sources and included energy sources such as firewood, solar, electricity and Liquefied Petroleum Gas (LPG). The study also focused on fully serviced houses in high density residential suburbs. Wind energy, geothermal, tidal energy and nuclear energy were excluded.

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A descriptive survey research design was employed for the study and a mixed paradigm approach was employed, thus both secondary and primary data were used. Primary data were gathered through formal surveys which were based on structured questionnaires. The questionnaires' targeted respondents were household heads. In the absence of the head of household a mature representative (18years and above) of the household was selected to fill in the questionnaire on behalf of the household head. The questionnaires were administered to 120 randomly selected households in 3 of the pre-selected high density residential suburbs namely Rujeko (Cherima), Rusike (Phase1), and Cherutombo of the town. Forty respondents were selected in each of the three residential areas. Informal interviews with the residents were also done during the administration of the questionnaires. Descriptive statistics were used in data analysis.

2.1. Description of the study area

Marondera is a small town that is situated about 75km East of Harare the capital city of Zimbabwe and has a population of about 62 120 (CSO, 2012). Marondera urban is divided into 12 administrative wards and the average household size is 3.7 and the total number of households is 16 700. The town is agro-based and thrives on both commercial farming. Marondera is situated in Zimbabwe's agro-ecological Region 2 which is characterised by moderately high rainfall and the rainy season stretches from October to March.

3. RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Gender characteristics of the Respondents

88% of the respondents were females and 12% were male though 82% of the households were male headed. The average household size for the study area is 5people. The results of the study show that the residents of Marondera are literate and generally educated as only 13 respondents indicated that they have no form of formal education. Table 1 below indicates the distribution of respondents by level of education.

Figure1: Level of Education for the Respondents

3.2 Distribution of the respondents by age

The age groups of the respondents ranged from below 20 to above 50 years. A greater % (53%) of the respondents was in the age range of 31 to 40 years. Table 1 shows the distribution of respondents by age.

Table 1: Distribution of the respondents by age

Age Group	Number of Respondents	(%)
Below 20	3	3
20-30	25	21
31-40	64	53
41-50	17	14
50 and above	11	9
Total	120	100

3.3 Respondents' main source of income

On being asked about their main source of household income, 43% of the respondents indicated that they are formally employed and 39% indicated that they are informally employed and 18% indicated that they are not employed at all. The informal source of income identified included selling various items ranging from vegetables, food stuffs, clothing, firewood, and bricks to mention but a few.

The research findings indicated that household incomes are generally low as more than half of the total number of respondents (64%) indicated that their household incomes are less than USD500. The situation in Marondera depicts Zimbabwe's economic situation has been characterised by unemployment and underemployment such that many people's income fall below the poverty datum line for Zimbabwe.

3.4 Marondera residents' main sources of household energy

93 % representing 112 respondents indicated that their main source of energy was electricity. While 7% representing 8 respondents indicated that their main source of energy for household purposes was firewood. The results indicate that there is lack of diversity in energy sources and that electricity is the main source of energy for the residents of Marondera. Despite the fact that most people in Marondera are depended on electricity for their energy needs, its supply has become unreliable such that it is common for Marondera Urban area to be without electricity for more than 12 hours on Mondays, Wednesday and Fridays. In the absence of the main energy source respondents indicated that they depend on firewood, gas, firewood, solar, paraffin and diesel generator. The results are shown in Table 2. The research study concur with the Zimbabwe national energy balance of 2009 indicated that wood fuel provided the bulk (61%) of the total energy supply, followed by liquid fuels (18%), electricity (13%), and coal (8%) (Zimbabwe National Energy Policy, (undated).

Table 2: Other sources of energy (in the absence of the main source)

Energy Source	Number of Respondents	%
Firewood	106	88
Gas	37	31
Solar	90	75
Paraffin	7	6
Diesel Generator	3	3

All the respondents who indicated that they use firewood for their domestic purposes only indicated that they use solar energy for lighting purposes only. Though Zimbabwe's solar energy potential is great, it is underexploited not only in Marondera but nationwide. This is due to the high up-front cost which many users cannot afford.

The research also discovered that though the main source of energy was electricity, the residents employed a mix of energy options which included electricity, gas and firewood (most common mix). The concept of energy mix is defined by Mirza and Sirzimai (2010) as the proportion of different energy sources used by households to meet their energy needs. The findings indicate that firewood remains an important source of energy even across different income groups for the respondents and to confirm this, small temporary shelters (make-shift structures) used as kitchens during the absence of electricity adjacent to the main houses were observed during the administration of the questionnaires. While the energy ladder model assumes that as income level increases energy users will switch from solid and traditional unclean fuels to cleaner modern fuels (Ekouevi and Tuntivate, 2012); the research showed that households continue to use a variety of energy sources

simultaneously regardless of income levels. This implies the interplay of different factors in energy source preference apart from income levels. The Zimbabwe National Energy Policy, (undated) reiterates that wood fuel will continue to be used for cooking and space heating by rural and low-income urban households for the foreseeable future. This is however against a background of diminishing forests.

A relatively smaller percentage (31%) of the respondents indicated that they use LPG. This is a result of the fact that LPG is generally expensive (especially for bigger families) costing about USD 2.50 to USD3per kg apart from the initial capital outlay (gas cylinder and or plate). The other possible reason for low usage of LPG by the respondents can be due to the fact that most Zimbabweans generally associate LPG with explosions and as such safety is a contributory factor to the use of LPG by the residents. The Zimbabwe Energy Regulatory Authority (ZERA) has been educating and encouraging the public to use LPG through the media.

3.5 Main household uses of the energy sources

Though the research was focussed on household energy the researcher sought to identify the actual household uses (cooking, heating, cooling, lighting, etc) to which the different energy sources are being put to use. All the respondents who indicated that electricity was their main source of energy indicated that they use electricity for cooking, heating, cooling, lighting, ironing and electrical and the operation of electronics (television sets, radios, decoders, DVD players, etc). LPG users indicated that they use it mainly for cooking. Respondents indicated that they use solar energy and candles (87%) for lighting and charging cell phone batteries. Candles still play a significant in meeting lighting needs of the households. No solar powered household gadgets were owned by the respondents apart from solar lamps. These findings concur with IEA (2014) which indicated that households in Sub Saharan Africa (SSA) prioritised cooking and lighting such that around 80% of residential energy demand in (SSA) is for cooking.

3.6 Factors influencing access to alternative sources of energy by the residents of Marondera

Respondents indicated that the access and use of alternative sources of energy has been a result of two factors namely availability and cost of the energy sources. All the respondents indicated that availability and the cost of the energy source are the major factors influencing the accessibility and use of energy sources in Marondera Urban. In other words, the residents' options are limited to what is available. While availability is necessary, it is worth noting that it is not an end in itself. The results also indicate a positive relationship between the type of energy source and the residents' amount of income (household). All the households (respondents) which indicated firewood as their main source of energy earn less than USD200 and they use open fire for their domestic purposes. Though wood is the cheapest in terms of its actual financial cost the users pay more than users of other expensive and cleaner energy sources because of its (wood fuel) inefficiency. Mirza and Sirzimai (2010) argue that poor households pay more for energy when they use traditional and less efficient energy sources. Studies on energy and income relationship have also indicated that as household income increases, households tend to shift from inconvenient and inefficient energy sources to more modern, convenient and efficient sources (Mirza and Sirzimai, 2010). Total dependence on traditional energy sources can give a hint on the income of the user when the user is exposed to other energy options. Thus though the use of poor energy sources may not reflect income poverty, the use of cleaner and more efficient sources do give a reflection of the amount of household income.

3.7 Energy challenges faced by the residents

Unavailability and lack of reliability of Zimbabwe Electricity Supply Authority (ZESA)- supplied electric power were the main household energy challenges identified by the respondents. A relatively smaller proportion of the respondents (25%) indicated energy cost as a challenge. These challenges have resulted in the residents having to search for other energy options and in the process incur extra financial costs considering the fact that the ZESA supplied electricity is pre-paid. This means that the residents are paying for energy that is not available such that they then need to spare extra finances towards other energy sources. The poorer residents also have to invest more time towards cleaning of pots and pans as well as searching for cheaper energy options such as firewood.

3.8 Residents' coping strategies to the energy challenges

The main energy source (electricity) in Marondera urban is not reliable and other cleaner energy sources are expensive for the low income earners and large households, as a result residents employ a variety of coping strategies to the challenges they face. The coping strategies employed by residents include using cheaper energy options, reducing overall energy (cleaner) consumption and reducing the overall living expenses as well as preparing some meals earlier (before electricity is switched off). The results are shown in Table below

Table 3: Coping strategies employed by the residents

Coping strategy	%
Switching to cheaper energy options (energy mix)	89
Reducing overall consumption of energy	33
Preparing meals early	87

The results confirm that though the cost of energy has a significant role to play, its availability and reliability are equally important hence the use of a variety of energy sources by the residents.

4. CONCLUSION

Electricity is the main source of energy for the residents of Marondera but due to its unavailability and lack of reliability, there is still heavy reliance on traditional fuels (mainly firewood) as access to alternative sources of energy by the residents of Marondera is limited and influenced mainly by the availability and cost of the energy sources. According to Ekouevi and Tuntivate (2012), over-reliance on solid fuels and traditional fuels is an indicator of energy poverty. The main conclusion of the study is therefore that the residents of Marondera are generally energy poor as they lack sufficient choices in accessing adequate, affordable, reliable, clean, high quality, safe and benign energy services for household purposes.

5. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the conclusions made by this study, the following recommendations are made;

- Energy poverty can be reduced through improving the availability of alternative and modern energy sources and increasing the access to those sources through reducing financial poverty. The government should come up with pro-poor energy policies and pro-poor solutions to energy problems
- The government should increase more players in the energy sector. This can be done through fostering public and private sector partnerships in the sector.
- The government should also promote small scale hydropower stations so that in the event of shortages or failure of the large stations regions of the country are spared.
- There is also need for individual researchers and institutions to carry out more research on different energy sources to increase the energy options for the nation.
- ZERA and other responsible institutions should continue providing information on the different energy options that are available to the urban residents to reduce reliance on electricity and traditional fuels.

REFERENCES

- Ekouevi K. and Tuntivate V. (2012). World Bank Studies: Household Energy Access for Cooking and Heating: Lessons Learned and the Way Forward. The World Bank, Washington DC.
- IEA (2014) Africa Energy Outlook- A Focus on Energy Prospects in Sub-Saharan Africa. World Energy Outlook Special Report, OECD/IEA, Paris, France. www.iea.org/publications/freepublications/publication/WEO2014_AfricaEnergyOutlook.pdf accessed on 28 January 2014.
- IEA/UNDP/UNIDO (2010). Energy poverty-How to make modern energy accessible? Special Excerpt of the World Energy Outlook 2010 for the UN General Assembly for the Millennium Development Goals OECD/IEA, Paris, France.
- Mirza B and Sirzimai A (2010). Towards a new measurement of Energy Poverty: A Cross- Community Analysis of Rural Pakistan, United Nations University www.econjournals.com/index.php/ijeep/article/viewFile/645/384 accessed on 28 January 2014.
- UNDP/WHO (2009). The energy access situation in developing countries, A Review Focusing on the Least Developed Countries and Sub-Saharan Africa WHO/UNDP.
- World Bank (2010) Energy Poverty in Rural and Urban India: Are the Energy Poor Also Income Poor? Policy Research Working Paper 5463 <http://elibrary.worldbank.org/doi/pdf/10.1596/1813-9450-5463> accessed on 27 January 2015.
- Wodon Q. and Blackden C. M. (2006). Gender, Time Use, and Poverty in Sub-Saharan Africa. World Bank, Washington DC.
- Zimbabwe Ministry of Energy and Power Development. (Undated). National Energy Policy.

Cite this Article: Madobi R. (2016). An Assessment of Energy Poverty in Zimbabwe's Urban Communities: The Case of Marondera. Greener Journal of Environmental Management and Public Safety, 5(1):001-006, <http://doi.org/10.15580/GJEMPS.2016.1.121115166>.